

Sustainable Frameworks Analysis For The Circularity And Recyclability Assessment Of Buildings

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Abstract. The construction industry is a major contributor to resource depletion, greenhouse gas emissions, and waste generation, emphasizing the need for circularity and sustainability in building practices. Circular design strategies, including material reuse, recyclability, and disassembly, play a crucial role in reducing reliance on virgin materials and minimizing environmental impact. However, the absence of standardized evaluation frameworks limits the ability to measure and compare circularity performance effectively. This study reviews existing assessment frameworks and technical standards relevant to circularity and recyclability in construction, identifying their strengths and limitations. It categorizes these frameworks into sustainability-focused, material-specific, health and well-being, and technical standards, highlighting the importance of key performance indicators. The analysis underscores the importance of integrating lifecycle-based methodologies, material traceability, and regulatory compliance to enhance circularity assessment. By providing a structured evaluation of existing methodologies, this work aims to bridge knowledge gaps and support the development of standardized tools for measuring circularity in buildings. The findings contribute to better policy alignment and decision-making, facilitating the transition towards a circular economy in the built environment.

1. Introduction

1.1. Context

The buildings and construction sector is a major contributor to resource depletion, greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, and waste generation, accounting for 37% of global energy and process-related CO₂ emissions [1], with 11% stemming from the production of building materials and products for construction and renovation [2]. In the EU, construction industry represents nearly half of all extracted materials [3]. This underscores the urgent need for low-impact materials, circular design strategies, and efficient resource management to mitigate environmental impacts. A crucial component of this transition is the reuse and recycling of construction and demolition waste (CDW), which includes materials such as concrete, bricks, wood, metals, plastics, and soil.

CDW accounts for 35.7% of total waste generation and almost 40% of the EU's waste [4], making it a key element in reducing primary material extraction and carbon emissions associated with construction activities. However, despite the potential benefits of circular models in construction, their adoption remains limited due to barriers such as uncertainties in CDW management, concerns about the quality of recycled materials, and perceived health risks for workers and building users.

To monitor the circularity rate, Eurostat introduced the *circular material use rate*, which quantifies the proportion of materials in the EU derived from recycled waste [5]. In 2023, this rate was 11.8%, reflecting an increase of 3.6 percentage points since 2004 [6]. While this shows gradual progress, it remains insufficient to meet the EU's climate neutrality targets for 2050 [7]. To bridge this gap, policy integration, enhanced material recovery processes, and lifecycle-based evaluation methodologies are needed to accelerate circularity within the built environment.

1.2. Research Gap

Despite the growing recognition of circular economy principles in the construction sector, there is a significant lack of a common framework for assessing circularity and recyclability in buildings. This gap translates into limitations in measuring and comparing progress towards circularity, as well as a lack of well-established KPIs focusing on energy efficiency, material reuse, recyclability, and waste reduction. Existing methodologies vary widely in scope, metrics, and applicability, making it challenging to adopt a standardised approach for evaluating circular construction strategies. Many current assessment frameworks focus on specific aspects such as energy efficiency, material reuse, or waste reduction, but fail to provide a holistic perspective that integrates all relevant KPIs. This fragmentation limits comparability across studies and hinders stakeholders' ability to make informed decisions regarding circular construction practices.

Moreover, there is limited research on how circularity metrics align with lifecycle-based evaluation methodologies, especially concerning material recovery processes and policy integration. The absence of harmonised criteria further complicates efforts to assess the effectiveness of circular strategies and track progress towards sustainability goals at regional, national, and EU levels. To address this gap, it is essential to develop a standardised evaluation framework that encompasses a comprehensive set of KPIs, ensuring consistency in measuring circularity performance. Such a framework is essential to support better policy alignment, enable informed decision-making for industry professionals, and ultimately enhance the scalability and effectiveness of circular solutions in the built environment.

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This research, developed within the scope of the SIRCULAR project [8], aims to bridge these gaps by analysing existing assessment frameworks, identifying their strengths and weaknesses in supporting the transition to a circular economy, and extracting relevant Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). The SIRCULAR project itself provides a central reference for the definitions, methodologies, and KPIs considered in this study, ensuring alignment with EU policies and best practices in circular construction. The ultimate goal is to advance standardized evaluation tools and integrate circularity metrics into sustainable building design and policy frameworks.

2. Methodology

To evaluate circularity and recyclability in construction, the methodology (Figure 1) proposed analyses a selection of established assessment frameworks and standards. The methodology presented in this paper builds on the definitions and approaches developed within the SIRCULAR project. The selection and categorisation of assessment frameworks were guided by SIRCULAR's criteria for evaluating circularity in buildings, ensuring that the chosen frameworks align with the project's objectives and the EU's sustainability priorities, as well as relevance to circular economy principles, and application in sustainable building design and material efficiency.

Figure 1. Methodology for the circularity assessment frameworks analysis.

Within the selection of the suitable frameworks, these were categorised into four main groups according to their primary focus and methodological approach:

- **Sustainability-focused frameworks:** LEED, BREEAM, Green Star, and LEVEL(s) provide comprehensive sustainability assessments, addressing energy efficiency, water conservation, material impact, and waste management. While LEED, BREEAM, and Green Star are certification systems, LEVEL(s) serves as an EU framework that integrates lifecycle environmental performance with a particular focus on carbon metrics and resource efficiency.
- **Circularity and material-focused frameworks:** Cradle to Cradle, Material Passport, and the Material Circularity Indicator specifically assess material performance, recyclability, and lifecycle efficiency. These frameworks emphasise design for reuse and closed-loop systems, prioritising material recovery and adaptability.
- **Occupant health and well-being frameworks:** WELL building standard and the Living Building Challenge focus on indoor environmental quality, human health, and regenerative sustainability. Although their primary focus is not circularity, they contribute to sustainable material choices and lifecycle considerations.
- **Technical standards:** ISO 14001 (environmental management), ISO 59020 (circular economy), and ISO 20887 (design for disassembly and adaptability) establish guidelines for integrating circular practices into construction. While these are not certification schemes, they provide best practices that underpin several of the frameworks analysed.

The evaluation of each framework's alignment with circularity principles was based on a qualitative analysis of how they address the five key circularity elements identified (material reuse/recyclability, adaptability, lifecycle integration, material tracking, and circular economy alignment).

3. Review of Circularity Assessment Frameworks

3.1. Overview of Selected Frameworks

In reviewing the selected assessment frameworks, this study specifically focuses on how each framework addresses key circularity elements: material reuse and recyclability, design for

adaptability and disassembly, integration of lifecycle thinking, material tracking and transparency, and overall alignment with circular economy principles [9].

LEED [10] is a globally adopted certification scheme developed by the U.S. Green Building Council, focusing on sustainable building practices and environmental performance across multiple categories. LEED encourages use of materials with recycled content and waste reduction but lacks emphasis on reuse or material loops. It provides limited guidance on DfAD (Design for Adaptability and Disassembly) and does not explicitly support modular or flexible building design. LEED partially supports circular economy goals through LCA and material selection strategies, but does not embed circularity as a core concept. In fact, it includes optional credits for LCA, allowing for environmental impact assessment, but this is not central in the rating system.

BREEAM [11] is one of the most widely used building certification systems in Europe, offering credits across environmental performance areas. It places a stronger emphasis on circularity. BREEAM provides credits for using reclaimed materials and managing construction waste effectively. It includes criteria encouraging long-term flexibility and ease of future modification. Lifecycle assessment and lifecycle costing are central components, with clear links to design decisions. BREEAM shows strong alignment with circularity principles, especially in its integration with EU sustainability targets and its support for modular design and LCA-based decisions.

Green Star [12] is an Australian green building rating tool administered by the Green Building Council of Australia, adapted to regional conditions and priorities. It includes credits for reducing construction waste and using recycled content but does not promote reuse beyond material selection. Moreover, it encourages modular design principles but lacks prescriptive DfAD criteria and supports LCA in assessing the environmental footprint of building materials. Material provenance is addressed but lacks the depth of traceability seen in EU frameworks. While promoting some aspects of circularity, Green Star aligns partially with circular principles and remains focused on local environmental and health outcomes.

LEVEL(s) [13] is a policy-driven framework by the European Commission aimed at integrating sustainability and circularity into building assessments across the EU. It encourages reduction of material demand and supports strategies for reuse through circular design indicators and includes flexibility and adaptability criteria, with guidance on reversible design. LCA and LCC are core tools, ensuring a systems-level view from early design phases. LEVEL(s) supports reporting of key resource flows but lacks prescriptive tracking systems like passports. It is one of the most comprehensive frameworks aligning with EU circular economy goals, facilitating policy harmonization and scalable circular implementation.

For material-specific circularity, the **Cradle to Cradle (C2C)** is a product-level certification system assessing material health, circularity, renewable energy use, water stewardship, and social fairness. C2C evaluates materials based on their potential for safe, continuous cycling in biological or technical loops. It focuses on material flows rather than full environmental LCA; lifecycle coverage is partial. It provides strong alignment with circular principles at product level, but limited applicability at whole-building scale unless integrated with broader frameworks.

Material Passports (MPs) [14] are digital tools aimed at documenting and communicating information on material properties to support reuse and circularity. They emerged from EU initiatives such as Buildings As Material Banks (BAMB). MPs provide key data on material composition and reuse potential, though they do not directly evaluate recyclability. MPs support lifecycle thinking by enabling data collection for environmental and performance assessments. Its core function is offering granular material traceability throughout the building lifecycle.

Therefore, they are enablers of circularity through data infrastructure. They are best used in combination with other assessment frameworks, as they lack prescriptive evaluation capabilities.

Similarly, the **Material Circularity Indicator (MCI)** [15], developed by the Ellen MacArthur Foundation, is a metric designed to quantify the circularity of products based on mass flows and utility. MCI measures input from recycled sources and the potential for material recovery, but it does not address DfAD directly and assumes end-of-use recovery without considering reversibility in design. One of its biggest challenges is the need of accurate material data but does not prescribe tracking systems or tools. MCI offers a quantifiable indicator for circularity performance but is best suited as a complementary tool, not a full evaluation framework.

Lastly, frameworks such as the **WELL Building Standard** and the **Living Building Challenge (LBC)** focus primarily on occupant health and well-being, with limited attention to material circularity. Although LBC addresses aspects of waste minimization through its “Net Positive Waste” criteria, and WELL considers material exposure in indoor environments, these frameworks do not provide a structured approach to material reuse or lifecycle performance.

ISO 14001 is an international standard for environmental management systems (EMS), focusing on continuous improvement and impact reduction across operations. It encourages strategies to minimize material use and promote waste prevention, but does not define reuse metrics. 14001 contributes indirectly to circularity by embedding environmental considerations in operations, though it lacks design- or material-specific prescriptions.

ISO 59020 is a recent standard that provides guidance for measuring circularity performance through indicators and data reporting. It establishes indicators for material inflows/outflows, recovery rates, and recyclability. Its strong emphasis is on lifecycle-based metrics across supply chains and product stages. ISO 59020 directly supports circular economy monitoring efforts and offers a consistent measurement approach, though its operationalization in buildings is still emerging.

Lastly, **ISO 20887:2020** fills a critical gap by focusing explicitly on design for disassembly and adaptability. This standard emphasizes the importance of designing building components that can be easily deconstructed and reused at the end of their lifecycle, extending material lifespan and minimizing waste. It details recommendations for recyclable materials and modular construction make it a strong complement to the broader sustainability and lifecycle frameworks.

Overall, this comparative analysis highlights that while frameworks like BREEAM and LEVEL(s) offer robust pathways for integrating circularity at the building level, particularly through lifecycle thinking and material reuse, others like LEED and Green Star have more limited emphasis on design for future adaptability. Meanwhile, material-specific tools like MP and MCI contribute valuable metrics and data but require integration with broader assessment frameworks to fully address the circularity of building systems. This underscores the need for harmonised criteria and comprehensive evaluation methodologies that can integrate these various circularity elements to support decision-making and policy alignment in the transition towards a more circular built environment.

4. Discussion

In the context of the SIRCULAR project, and considering the analysed frameworks related to the integral certification for sustainability in buildings (LEED, BREEAM, Green Star and LEVEL(s)), LEVEL(s) and BREEAM emerge as the most suitable frameworks, according to Table 1. This is due to its strong alignment with circular economy principles and European policies, particularly in areas such as design for disassembly, deep renovation, and lifecycle impact management. Green

Star provides valuable contributions with its focus on materials, modularity, and waste recovery, but its regional emphasis on Australia and New Zealand limits its direct applicability to European contexts. LEED, while highly recognised globally and strong in energy efficiency and carbon management, lacks the depth of focus on circularity offered by BREEAM and Green Star. Together, these frameworks can complement each other, with BREEAM leading the way in addressing SIRCULAR’s objectives of circularity, resource optimisation, and alignment with EU regulations.

Regarding circularity and material-focused frameworks, MCI contributes the most for the calculation of the material circularity and recyclability thanks to the well-established index to obtain the rank of a recycled / reused material (0 (linear) to 1 (circular)). However, it requires an external database; hence, MP emerges as a key player in the assessment of sustainability and circularity in buildings. It covers the full material life cycle, fostering the traceability and

Table 1. Summary of the sustainability frameworks.

Framework	Circularity focus	Strengths	Weaknesses	Application scope
LEED	Strong focus on LCA, material reuse, recyclability, and design for disassembly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Aligned with EU circular economy policies - Encourages adaptability and deconstruction - Uses LCA for material efficiency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lower emphasis on operational energy efficiency than LEED - Primarily Europe-focused, limiting global adoption 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Applied mainly in Europe - Covers new buildings, refurbishments, and large-scale developments
BREEAM	Incorporates circularity, but focuses more on energy efficiency and carbon management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strong energy efficiency and carbon benchmarks - Globally recognised, especially in America - Supports waste management and material reuse 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Less emphasis on lifecycle circularity - Prioritises operational performance over material adaptability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Used internationally, especially in America - Applied to new construction, existing buildings, and operational sustainability
Green Star	Supports recyclability and modular design, incorporating LCA and closed-loop material sourcing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Encourages reuse, disassembly, and material recovery - Integrates LCA for material impact assessment - Holistic sustainability framework covering multiple environmental aspects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Primarily used in Australia and New Zealand, limiting global adoption - Less alignment with European policies, making it less relevant in EU-based circularity initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Applied mainly in Australia and New Zealand - Covers new buildings, refurbishments, and interior fit-outs
LEVEL(s)	Strong focus on LCA and LCC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Aligned with EU circular economy policies - Large availability of KPIs for evaluation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Not able for large scale projects - Less emphasis in materials 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EU focus - Covers new buildings and renovation projects

Table 2. Summary of the circularity and material-focused frameworks.

Framework.	Circularity focus	Strengths	Weaknesses	Application scope
Cradle to Cradle (C2C)	Good practises to minimize the environmental impact and increase sustainability	- Measures materials toxicity, water consumption and recyclability ratio	- Lower emphasis on the materials circularity, such a reusability	- Materials value chain
Material Passport (MP)	Materials databases with the characterisation of the materials	- Keeping track of the materials to ensure traceability and transparency for their reuse	- Only used as a material database, without focus on the recyclability levels	- Materials lifecycle
Material Circularity Indicator (MCI)	Analysis of the recycled and reused materials	- Well-defined index for recyclability of materials	- Only providing guidelines how to calculate the index - Requiring external material databases	- Materials lifecycle

transparency of the materials. MCI in combination with MP allows contractors to take informed decisions about materials, how to recycle and reuse them, reducing the waste in the end of their life cycle. Last but not least, C2C, despite its benefits, provides similar features than the previous frameworks, but with lower emphasis in circularity and recyclability, as observed in Table 2.

In terms of occupant health and well-being, neither WELL nor LBC are proper frameworks to analyse the circularity of buildings. Although they contain some aspects related to materials, such as “Net positive waste” within the Imperative 16 of LBC and human exposure to chemicals in WELL, these aspects are already addressed by other frameworks previously analysed.

Finally, regarding technical standards, all of them share a clear objective related to decarbonization. ISO 14001 primarily focuses on internal organizational management and may require adaptations to fully address the specific technical challenges of the construction sector. ISO 59020, with its emphasis on resource efficiency, recyclability, and sustainability, serves as a valuable tool, especially when integrated with project-specific factors such as social impact and innovative construction technologies. ISO 20887 is particularly relevant for strategies aimed at extending material lifespan and minimizing waste via adaptability and design for disassembly.

5. Conclusions

The transition towards circularity and sustainability in the construction sector requires robust and standardised evaluation frameworks capable of effectively measuring material recyclability, resource efficiency, and environmental impact. While existing methodologies offer valuable insights, they often lack a unified approach that integrates KPIs across different stages of a building’s life cycle. The fragmented nature of current frameworks limits comparability, making it challenging for stakeholders to assess the effectiveness of circular strategies. Strengthening policy alignment, improving material tracking systems, and adopting lifecycle assessment tools are essential to enhance the impact of circular economy principles in the built environment.

The analysis of sustainability-focused, material-specific, and technical standards highlights the importance of integrating circularity within broader environmental performance metrics.

Frameworks such as LEVEL(s) and BREEAM demonstrate strong alignment with circular economy principles, particularly in Europe, whereas other methodologies, such as Cradle to Cradle and the Material Passport, offer material-specific insights that enhance transparency and traceability. Despite these strengths, achieving a fully circular construction sector requires harmonisation between assessment frameworks, regulatory standards, and industry practices.

Future efforts should prioritise the development of a comprehensive assessment methodology that bridges existing gaps, ensuring consistency in circularity measurement. Incorporating adaptability, material traceability, and design for disassembly will be crucial in reducing construction-related waste and emissions. Moreover, integrating social impact considerations and innovative construction technologies into evaluation frameworks will further support a holistic transition to circularity. A structured, standardised approach will enable policymakers, industry professionals, and researchers to make informed decisions, accelerating the shift towards a sustainable and resource-efficient built environment.

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